

Reactivity Hypothesis adult reactivity versus child reactivity

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H_0 Null Hypothesis

Case 1. Adult reactivity → internal contra response without explicit 'no' → suppresses behavior (intensified self-self salience)

Case 2. Adult reactivity if being explicitly told 'no' → suppresses behavior* (intensified self-self salience)

*non-pathological individual

Case 1. Child reactivity if not explicitly told 'no' → no contra response (no intensification)

Case 2. Child reactivity if explicitly told 'no' → contra response → intensifies behavior

It is thought that the difference is that the adults are not told to 'not say a given word' (they salience themselves already) and if they are non-pathological and are old no, they have acquired, learned to obey and also salience themselves. Leading to the same outcome.

Whereas the children are not monitoring themselves the way adults do, likely due to a pre-mature prefrontal cortex (PFC), at least not monitoring themselves in the same mature intensity, so only if they are explicitly told not to say a given word they intensify their behavior.

Abstract

The phenomenon of reactivity is such that if one tells a person that the person is recorded each time the person says the word 'like' the person is saying it less than if the person would have not known the word is going to be recorded, i.e. the person being monitored. A good example is described in the book **David H. Barlow & V. Mark Durand, 2012, 2009 *Abnormal Psychology An Integrative Approach*, Wadsworth, Cengage Learning, p.77, ISBN-13: 978-1-111-34520-4:**

"A phenomenon known as reactivity can distort any observational data. Any time you observe how people behave, the mere fact of your presence may cause them to change their behavior (Haynes et al., 2009). To test reactivity, you can tell a friend you are going to record every time she says the word like. Just before you reveal your intent, however, count the times your friend uses this word in a 5-minute period. You will probably find that your friend uses the word less often when you are recording it. Your friend will react to the observation by changing the behavior. The same phenomenon occurs if you observe your own behavior, or self-monitor. Behaviors people want to increase, such as talking more in class, tend to increase, and behaviors people want to decrease, such as smoking, tend to decrease when they are self-monitored (for example, Hufford, Shields, Shiffman, Paty, & Balabanis, 2002). Clinicians sometimes depend on the reactivity of self-monitoring to increase the effectiveness of their treatments."

Now we can wonder if this is a salience response of the adult, since the person now is aware of being monitored.

In contrast to that if young children, receive an external no, an external salience response, they are intensifying whatever they are old not to do.

Now could it be possibly true that this is due to the same salience network, being fully matured in the grown ups and being not yet fully developed in the children and therefore even an external salience, a 'no' creates a contra response?

And is the behavior of the adult being watched or documented also the same type of contra response (intensifying self-salience)?

Could it be that it is not simply being aware of the word being recorded, but also subconsciously a contra response (intensifying self-salience)?

Then this would imply that the reply is opposite in different stages of maturation, the adult contra response is internally intensifying self-salience, probably caused in the subconscious and the child contra response is external intensification, probably also caused in the subconscious.

Method

This Hypothesis, of course, has to be statistically tested in a big group of people. People belonging to either the children(age <10) or adult group.

The age in children is thought to be important to be age <10, because the Default Mode Network (DMN) and the Central Executive Network (CEN), important for meta-cognition and self-monitoring, "developed stronger internal connectivity from age 10 to 13." (Lauren E Sherman a, 2014)

Contribution of idea

I, the author (without resources other than ideas), still wants to contribute this hypothesis regarding the psychology of reactivity and therefore freely share the hypothesis to be scrutinized, tested by anybody who has the resources, the ability and the wish to spend time and effort on the psychological causes of the reactivity-phenomenon.

Sources

Lauren E Sherman a, b. J. (2014, august 20). *National Library Of Medicine*. doi:doi:10.1016/j.dcn.2014.08.002